

Signal sequence

```

OGN1_S.aurata : ---MKSLIFTCMLVP-WLAAASARKSDQ-----DSQLIVGSLPGRELNGYFS---DP--LNSRR-----ARRAVS-LADEPDDS--PVSEGG-DASD LPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 89
OGN1_O.niloticus : MLDSMKTLFFTCMLVP-WLVAASDRT-----KYLDC-----IKPKS-----EKRALP-PADEPDDN--PITAGA-DAAD LPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 74
OGN1_G.morhua : ---MTTVVFLCLLVP-WLATVSGNS-----LDQ-----KTQLI-LGRVPAGTELDYLES--RKTKLPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 63
OGN1_D.erio : MRTRLRMLIAAVVLVS-MVLSASGAHYHT-----HRHHRLEDVALTEETD---VRAQRNKRSTNGDDDKNALM-LADAPDDSG-PLQFVG-DPSD LPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 98
OGN2_S.aurata : MMQLRTLIFTYVILP-WILSSAAKD-----EFMEA-----RKPKEGVVT--YPDY---EEPATD--AAGDP--KADELPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 72
OGN2_O.niloticus : MIPLRTLIFTYVMLP-WIVSSAAKG-----EYMEA-----RTPKATVTR--ASDYG-ILQDITD--GGVPS--KAEV LPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 75
OGN2_G.morhua : --MHLEMLICVILIPSLVLCSPAKN-----GYIEA-----RAPKKDIVTIFEFPQD-LPAKPEAAGNMFSTKL-YNSVLPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 80
OGN2_D.erio : MLDLYATLFTTLTHQ-WLLLSCKCS-----PVLS-----KIPKKVILS---QDYD-NPADKDVE--IPGADP-KDDELPTCLMCVCLIGSVY : 74
OGN_L.oculatus : MSKLPKPLIFSLILVL-WVILAAVTAFTLDS-----EHHNNEKDFIRTPDD---FLTALAEKQETIIDYEDLPPADTEPAENEVPLPTPKAAELPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 101
OGN_L.chalumnae : --MLHPVLLLFMLVA-WWKAQPVDKDYFTVENVNLDFDENETGLETHDVIYGDYEGKEEPSTRKKESTPDTFLELLRPPRSPITIEPERVLTQDVDLPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 111
OGN_X.tropicalis : MQPLPVCCTLLLLLP-FILSAPSVPQQT-----ISHHEDYIVEGKLFQNLQ---KMAQTTERNGLTLLSKDRFK-RDQERAGSN-RTAAKV-EDADLPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 100
OGN_G.gallus : MKTLQAAFLLVAFVP-LVKEAPPQQDSPKFYEYVDADFATGSLIQDDYE--ML---PKDTIKDGTNVSL--DTALR-LQADDSSEL--SARPTK-DTN-LPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 101
OGN_H.sapiens : MKTLQSTLLLLLVP-LVKEAPPPTQDSRIIYDYGTDNFEES-IFSQDYEDKYL---DGNIKEKETVIIPNEKSLQ-LQKDEAIT--PLPPKK-ENDELPTCLLCVCLIGSVY : 105
    
```

* * * φ

L-motif 1

L-motif 2

L-motif 3

L-motif 4

L-motif 5

```

*
OGN1_S.aurata : CEEVSPDMSVPTLPKETAYLYARFNKIKKISTKDFAGILILKRIDTGNLISEIEDGAFSKLALLESLSLAENRLLVKLPLPAKLTSEFNANNF LKTRGVKANAFKKLTKLTHL : 204
OGN1_O.niloticus : CEEVSPDMSIPTLPKETAYLYARFNKIKKIKTKDFAEIVTLKRIDTGNLISEIEDGAFSKLTLLESLSLAENQLVKLPAKLTSEFNANYNLKTGKVKANAFKKLTKLANL : 189
OGN1_G.morhua : CEEVSPDMSVAPLPKETAYLYARFNKIKKIRSKDFADILILKRIDTGNLISEVEDGAFSKLPVLEELNLSNRLVKLPLPAKLTSEFNANYNLKTGKVKATAFKKLTRVNL : 178
OGN1_D.erio : CEEVDPDMSVPTLPKETAYLYARFNKIKKIKAKDFGDIVTLKRIDFTGNLISEIEDGAFSKLTMLESLSLAENQLAKLPLPAKLTSEFNANHNKLTGKVKANAFKKLNLKHL : 213
OGN2_S.aurata : CEEVSPBMSAVPALPKETAYLYARFNKIKKIRNSDFADMAPLRRIDTGNLISEIEDGAFSKLPDLEELILAEENKLRRLPMTKLVTFENANFNKLTQGVKATAFKKLTRSYL : 187
OGN2_O.niloticus : CEEVSPDMSAVPTLPKETAYLYARFNKIKKIHREDFADTALRRIDTGNLISEIEDGFSKLPNLEELKLAENRLLKLPMLPSKLVTFENANFNRLKTQGVKANAFKKLTRAYL : 190
OGN2_G.morhua : CEEVFPQMTAIPALPRETTYLYARFNKIKKIKNKDFADMGALKRIDTGNLISEIEDGAFSKLTNLEELFLAENRLLKLPMLPSKLTTLNANFNLLKSKGVRSNAFKKLPEAF : 195
OGN2_D.erio : CEEVSPDMSVPTLPKETAYLYARFNKIKKIKNKDFANIAILKRIDTGNLISEIEDGAFSKLHLEELTLAENRLLKLPMLPANLLSLDYNHNLLKTKGVKANAFKKLKILAYL : 189
OGN_L.oculatus : CEEVVPVITAVPALPKETAYLYARFNKIKKIAQKDFSEIPILRRIDTGNLISEIEDGAFSKLPQLEELSLAENRLLVKLPMLPKLTFENANHNRLRTRGVKANAFKKLVLN : 216
OGN_L.chalumnae : CEET--TIDSIAPALPKETAYLYARFNKIKKIKTKDFADIPILKVIDTGNLISEIEDGAFSKLLEALLLAENRLLTRIPALPKLQLEFNANNNRIKNGIKANAFKKLNN : 224
OGN_X.tropicalis : CEET--ETEEVPLPKETAYLYARFNKIKKIKAKDFSEFPILRRIDTGNLISEIEDGAFSKLPLLEQLAENRLLTRIPALPKLTFENANNDNOIKSKGIKANAFKKLTSAYL : 213
OGN_G.gallus : CEET--DIEAVPPLPKETAYLYARFNKIKKIAVSDFAIDITLRRIDEFGNISEIEDGAFSKLLEELSLAENRLLVKLPMLPKLTFENANQNRIRKSRGKNNAFKKLTLNAYL : 214
OGN_H.sapiens : CEEV--DIDAVPPLPKESAYLYARFNKIKKIKAKDFADIPNLRRLDFTGNLISEIEDGTFSLSLLEELSLAENQLLKLPLVLPKLTLEFNANKYKIKSRGIKANAFKKLNN : 218
    
```

L-motif 6

L-motif 7

* φ

```

OGN1_S.aurata : YLADNQLFAVP-QIPDSVQILHLONNIITEVNVDTFCRSNDTYLRLPSLNEVRLDGNPVVLSKNPDSFTCMKVLPSGRYR- : 282
OGN1_O.niloticus : FLADNMLEAVP-YIPESVRLHLHLONNIITEVNVDTFCRSNDTYLRLPSLNEVRLDGNPVVLSKYBDSFTCMKVLPSGKRYR- : 268
OGN1_G.morhua : FLADNQLFAVP-QIPESVRTLHLHLONNIITEVNVDTFCRSNDTYLRLPSLNEVRLDGNPVVLSKYBDSFICLRSPLPGRYR- : 257
OGN1_D.erio : YLAHNELEAVP-LIPETVRTLHLHLONNIISTVSTDTFCRSNDTYIRPNMNEIRMDGNPILNGQYBNSFICLQSLPIGRYQ- : 292
OGN2_S.aurata : YLGNNELEAVP-QLPESLNVVHLHLONNIISTIDEFTFCRSNDTYIRPNMNEIRMDGNPILNGQYBNSFICLETLPICGYN- : 266
OGN2_O.niloticus : YLGDNELEAVP-PLPESLNVVHLHLONNIISTIDEFTFCRSNDTYIRPNMNEIRMDGNPILNGQYBNSFICLQSLPIGRYK- : 269
OGN2_G.morhua : YLGNKLEVIP-QLPESLQIVHLHLONNIINTIDQTFCKGNTSYIRSTMEVRLDGNPLVLAQHNSFICLRNLPICGYY- : 274
OGN2_D.erio : YLGDNGLEAIP-PLPESLNVVHLHLONNIISTLDDTFCKGNTSYIRHNMQEVRLDGNPITLAQHNSFICLRALPTICGYY- : 268
OGN_L.oculatus : YLANNLEFAVPPHLPESLRLVHLHLONNIITAIIDEFTFCRSNDTYIRPNMNEIRLEGNPILGKYBNSFTCLKSLPMGYSYF- : 296
OGN_L.chalumnae : YLTHNLEKVPPIPDTRLVHLHLHLONNIITSIIDDTFCRSNDTYIRDCMDEIRMEGNPILAKFPNSFICLKLMPICGYY- : 304
OGN_X.tropicalis : YLANNLEFVQNLPELRLVHLHLONNIITLDDTFCKGNTSYIRSHMDEIRMEGNPILGKYBNSFTCLKSLPMGYSYF- : 294
OGN_G.gallus : YLGHNALEFVPLNLPESLRLVHLHLONNIITLDDTFCKGNTSYIRIRMEIRLEGNPILAKHVNAFSCLRLTPVGTYY- : 294
OGN_H.sapiens : YLDHNALEFVPLNLPESLRLVHLHLONNIITSIIDDTFCRSNDTYIRDRIEIRLEGNPILGKYBNSFICLRRLPIGYSYF- : 298
    
```